

Reflections of Narcissistic Personality Disorder on Work Life

Ozgul COMEZ¹

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¹ **Orcid ID: 0009-0007-7902-6738; Email : ozgulcomez@hotmail.com**

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Abstract

Narcissistic personality disorder characterized by self-admiration, arrogance, and condescension towards others. Numerous individuals may have narcissistic tendencies; however, narcissistic personality disorder is far more severe. Narcissistic qualities may manifest in regular individuals, but in narcissistic personality disorder, this phenomenon permeates all

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8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

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aspects of life. The narcissistic characteristics of these individuals are evident in their life, friendships, romantic connections, and all aspects of their everyday existence. Narcissistic personality disorder is more prevalent in males than in women. Seventy-five percent of all instances involve males.

Keywords: *Reflections of Narcissistic Personality, Narcissistic Disorder, Narcissistic, Work Life, Personality*

Purpose and Scope of the Study

This research aims to analyze the professional experiences of individuals with narcissistic personality disorder. The research seeks to benefit individuals with narcissistic personality disorder and provide recommendations for a successful professional life. This research used the Narcissistic Personality Disorder Inventory (NPI).

Methodology

Working Group

The research study group comprises 150 individuals, evenly divided into 75 women and 75 men, all employed in office settings throughout several regions.

Data Collection Tools

The Narcissistic Personality Inventory (NPI-13) was administered to a cohort of 150 individuals.

Process

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This scale has a three-dimensional structure and thirteen components. The rating scale extends from 1 = Strongly disagree to 6 = Strongly agree. The Jamovi software was used to ascertain the Cronbach Alpha coefficient and compute the sub-dimensions.

Literature Review and Conceptual Framework

The Concept of Narcissism

The etymology of the term Narcissist originates from Greek mythology, where the narrative is recounted as follows: Narcissus, who seen his own reflection in the river and became enamored with it, devoted his life to pursuing this unattainable love. Narcissus, unable to attain his unattainable desire, plunged into the river while attempting to embrace his own reflection and subsequently perished. The term Narcissism originates from this narrative. Narcissism was first delineated by Ellis in 1898 within the realm of psychology. A idea has been used for explanation.

Freud's paper "An Introduction to Narcissism" is a seminal work on the subject of narcissism.

b) What is the Definition of Narcissist?

American psychologist W. Keith Campbell, renowned for his contributions to the study of narcissism, characterizes narcissism as an exaggerated self-perception. In narcissistic personality disorder, the individual perceives himself as competent and robust in almost all external domains; nevertheless, underneath this façade, his self-worth is tenuous, and he has a sense of powerlessness. The individual consistently displays hubristic and self-aggrandizing habits, always anticipating accolades from others. Nonetheless, he is indifferent to the emotions of others and lacks the capacity for empathy. He sees others as entities to be controlled. Narcissistic individuals who see a lack of the attention they believe they merit experience unhappiness and disappointment, thus withdrawing from society. Concurrently, the society in which they reside marginalizes them owing to a lack of affection from individuals in their vicinity, attributable to its egocentric framework.

b) What is Narcissistic Personality Disorder?

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Narcissistic personality disorder is a psychiatric condition characterized by an individual's belief in their superiority over others in many domains, coupled with an excessive self-admiration and self-love. Numerous individuals may have narcissistic traits; however, narcissistic personality disorder is far more severe. Narcissistic traits may sometimes manifest in typical individuals, but in narcissistic personality disorder, this phenomenon permeates all aspects of life. The narcissistic traits of these individuals are evident in their lives, friendships, romantic connections, and all aspects of their everyday existence. Narcissistic personality disorder is far more prevalent in males than in women. Seventy-five percent of all instances involve males.

Narcissistic personality disorder, included among the 10 clinically recognized personality disorders, affects 1-5 percent of the population. Similar to other personality disorders, manifestations of narcissistic personality disorder often emerge between late adolescence and early adulthood. The symptoms shown by these people fluctuate according on the degree of the patient's condition.

1.2 What are the Etiologies of Narcissistic Personality Disorder?

Researchers have been unable to ascertain the precise etiology of narcissism. Narcissistic personality disorder is believed to arise from the interplay of genetic, environmental, social, and developmental variables. The factors at the junction are enumerated as follows: Childhood experiences include physical violence, sexual abuse, and psychological coercion. Excessive praise or severe judgment from parents or caregivers throughout childhood,

- a) *Personality and temperament,*
- b) *Inability to cope with stress,*
- c) *Lack of self-worth,*
- d) *Genetic tendency.*

At this juncture, let us elaborate on the topic of genetic predisposition. While little scientific evidence exists to establish a direct causal relationship between genetic structure and narcissistic personality disorder, research indicates that individuals with a familial history of

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this condition have a greater likelihood of developing it compared to those without such a background. The prevalence of sickness identified in a research on twins about 'twin personality disorders' indicated that the likelihood of the problem being hereditary is moderate to high. Research indicates that the likelihood of the condition being hereditary is greater among those with a familial history of the disease compared to those without.

Diagnosis of Narcissistic Personality Disorder

A psychologist or psychiatrist can ascertain whether you exhibit symptoms of narcissistic personality disorder. The insights garnered during discussions of your issues in sessions are often sufficient to ascertain if you possess this problem. If your expert identifies five of the following signs during interviews, a diagnosis of narcissistic personality disorder may be established.

- a) *Excessive self-importance, • Perceiving oneself as more successful, attractive, powerful, and intelligent than others, • Viewing oneself as superior to others and seeking association with others of elevated social standing.*
- b) *The need for social approval, • He believes he is entitled to all his accomplishments and future successes, • He does not hesitate to use others around him to fulfill his own ambitions.*
- c) *Deficiency of empathy, • Exhibitions of boastfulness that indicate elevated levels of hubris.*

Your mental health practitioner may use personality assessments to establish a diagnosis. To get a favorable outcome in personality assessments, the individual must respond accurately to the posed questions. Narcissistic personality disorder may co-occur with other psychiatric illnesses, complicating the diagnostic process. Other personality disorders often associated with narcissists include antisocial, borderline, schizotypal, and histrionic personality disorders. Moreover, a propensity for drug misuse is also seen.

1.4. What are the treatment options for Narcissistic Personality Disorder?

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Individuals with this personality disorder often lack awareness of their condition. The first and important stage in rehabilitation is for an individual to comprehend the impact of their activities on their own life and their interactions with others. Consequently, if there are relatives in your vicinity exhibiting the aforementioned symptoms, it is crucial to gently inform them about their condition as a kind of assistance. The primary component of treating narcissistic personality disorder is therapeutic sessions. The individual starts to recognize their own ideas and actions via this process. If the doctor you see identifies other issues such as anxiety and depression, antidepressant therapy may be included into the treatment plan. Your counselor may moreover suggest the incorporation of mood stabilizers and antipsychotic drugs together antidepressants. To affirm the need of therapy, assert that narcissistic personality disorder is a condition that unequivocally requires intervention. While you possess narcissistic tendencies, you will alienate others around you and undermine your connections. The fundamental insecurity will perpetually exhaust you. Through the therapy of narcissistic personality disorder, you will achieve self-acceptance and cultivate good connections with others in your vicinity.

1.5 Forms of Narcissism Narcissism has several forms, each exhibiting both shared and distinct traits.

1.5.1. Healthy Narcissism: Healthy narcissism is a typical condition seen in almost every individual. If it aligns with the facts, it poses no issue. Narcissism, conversely, manifests as an instinct that seeks to ascertain one's own worth and comprehend one's entitlements.

1.5.2. Grandiose Narcissism: Individuals exhibiting this trait accentuate their own competencies and moral superiority. This circumstance manifests as an obsession. They persist in their ostentatious demeanor, disregarding the impact on individuals in their vicinity.

1.5.3. Vulnerable or Delicate Narcissism: Grandiose Narcissism It is contrary. These individuals are often reticent and perceptive. Additional structural features include jealousy and excessive reactivity to external criticism. They exhibit excessive defensiveness and reactivity to criticism aimed at them. They exhibit quiet anger due to fear of rejection and feelings of guilt.

1.5.4. Sexual Narcissism: Individuals exhibiting sexual narcissism are preoccupied with their sexual performance. They need external validation for their performance and want admiration.

They use sexuality to influence those in their vicinity.

1.5.5. Somatic Narcissism: Somatic narcissists place excessive emphasis on their appearance.

Their attire, accessory choices, physical appearance, weight, and hairstyle are of paramount importance to these individuals. They see themselves as more attractive and robust than they really are. This framework leads them to critique others based on their looks.

1.5.6. Cerebral Narcissism:

In contrast to somatic narcissism, this kind emphasizes the intellectual attributes of an individual above their physical appearance. Primarily, they see themselves as more smart and intelligent than others. They see others as deficient in these domains and endeavor to instill this sentiment in those around them.

1.5.7. Spiritual Narcissism:

Individuals exhibiting this trait see their own views and spirituality as greater and more significant than those of others. They emphasize these traits and attempt to diminish the worth of others around them by adopting a superior demeanor.

1.5.8. Malignant Narcissism:

Malignant narcissism is the most perilous variant. This is the most detrimental kind of narcissism. Malignant narcissism encompasses antisocial personality characteristics, and sadism may also be included.

1.6. I exhibit narcissistic tendencies in relation to conducted research.

Engage in your life roles Narcissistic when analyzed in relation to its structural owner in observed persons. Profiles have significant importance. This personality exhibits a disease characterized by an elevated drive to excel. Individuals possess the capability to effectively

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execute assigned tasks, demonstrate high performance, and exhibit leadership abilities, therefore linking them to organizational behavior and narcissistic tendencies. There exists a very tight link. However, individuals with this personality condition possess elevated self-esteem, leading them to believe they occupy positions they do not have and lack the corresponding entitlement. If individuals do not extricate themselves from it, they will inevitably lead their professional life in a state of dissatisfaction and discontent. A clear correlation exists between workplace violence and narcissism. Let us not overlook. All studies conducted in this context Research and literary studies indicate a correlation between narcissism and work satisfaction. A robust inverse association was identified. The interaction between the two is characterized by a major distinction between exhibitionism and its inherent nature. It has been observed. The quality of the work and the sentiments of appreciation and superiority towards oneself are highly pronounced. The connection is in the other direction. The outcome has been revealed. A robust association exists between the exhibitionism and self-admiration facets of narcissism and A substantial correlation was identified. Narcissistic persons have a deficiency in empathy due to their propensity for making unsentimental, pragmatic judgments, which often contributes to their success. Fear of failure may be mitigated by more rigorous risk evaluation and the implementation of essential procedures, leading to increased success. It has been noted that they are. The link between leadership and narcissism is crucial and should not be overlooked.

2. Argument and Process-Data Analysis

Table 1. Narcissistic Personality Inventory-13 Values

Boyut	Madde	Ort	Ss	Düzeltilmiş Madde Toplam Korelasyonu		t	C.A
Liderlik/ Otorite	Madde 1	2.90	1.32	.45	.52	-10.93*	.78
	Madde 2	3.11	1.20	.64	.58	-15.67*	
	Madde 3	2.64	1.00	.61	.65	-13.41*	
	Madde 4	2.74	1.16	.54	.61	-13.24*	
Grandiyözite /Gösterişçilik	Madde 5	3.58	1.06	.40	.28	-8.67*	.72
	Madde 6	2.11	1.16	.43	.54	-9.96*	
	Madde 7	2.68	1.20	.56	.67	-14.31*	
	Madde 8	1.80	1.07	.37	.32	-7.88*	
	Madde 9	2.93	1.18	.56	.59	-13.52*	
Hak İddia Etme/ Sömürü	Madde 10	2.71	1.13	.39	.29	-8.45*	.61
	Madde 11	3.35	1.18	.53	.52	-10.28*	
	Madde 12	2.67	1.14	.25	.25	-5.10*	
	Madde 13	3.18	1.21	.55	.53	-12.77*	

* P < .05, C.A= Cronbach Alpha

The means of the scale items are analyzed, revealing that the means of the Narcissistic Personality Inventory-13 range from a minimum of 1.80 to a maximum of 3.58. The research evaluated NKE-13 across three dimensions: Leadership/Authority, Grandiosity/Ostentation, and Assertion/Exploitation.

The internal consistency coefficient of the scale was determined by calculating the Cronbach Alpha coefficient using the Jamovi tool. The Cronbach's Alpha internal consistency coefficient was determined to be .84, with sub-dimensions scoring .78 for Leadership/Authority, .72 for Grandiosity/Ostentation, and .61 for Entitlement/Exploitation; these data were acquired;

3. REFLECTIONS OF NARCISSISTIC PERSONALITY DISORDER ON WORK LIFE ACCORDING TO THE RESULTS OF THE RESEARCH

One cannot contend that an individual's demeanor in the workplace suffices for a clinical diagnosis. Establishing a good connection with a colleague or boss who has a narcissistic disposition is challenging. He is prepared to exploit anybody at any moment due to his inflated ego. When interacting with coworkers exhibiting narcissistic personality disorder, it is important to understand the appropriate actions and behaviors necessary for effective management.

3.1. Effective ways to work with a narcissistic individual

3.1.1 Trust what you feel

Typically, two categories of Narcissists are seen. The individual is extroverted. They are very charming persons. They receive praise from people. The second kind is somewhat more introverted, however they are exceptional individuals in their own right. If you see that some individuals are manipulating you at work, be aware that they may be narcissists. Numerous folks express a disdain for narcissistic persons who intrude into their life from the outset. Therefore, rely on your instincts.

3.1.2. Set Your Boundaries

If you perceive that your colleague is using you, that individual is likely a narcissist. They steal your ideas and claim them as their own; but, when you address this issue, they label you as excessively sensitive or accuse you of harboring envy. Uphold your limits with them and cultivate the ability to decline. Upon your refusal, a narcissist will ostracize you and redirect their attention towards others.

3.1.3. Giving Them Responsibilities

It is inconceivable for them to comprehend their errors, provide an apology, and derive a lesson. The more you attempt this, the more they will persist in ensnaring you in their schemes. Holding them responsible may entrap you in this detrimental circle.

3.1.4. Accept That They Will Never Change

One may aspire for their transformation and seek novel methods of persuasion; yet, it is essential to acknowledge that Narcissists are unlikely to change. Recent research indicate that the brains of narcissistic persons function differently. When engaging with these individuals, it is advisable to maintain a degree of distance in your interactions and conversations. Acquiring the ability to identify their manipulative tactics and establishing clear limits will assist you in managing them.

3.2.1. Let's also look at how these behavioral disorders can make themselves felt in an office;

- a) *They experience discomfort when subjected to inquiry or opposition.*
- b) *They possess an intense need for allegiance, commendation, and adulation.*
- c) *They welcome criticism and oppose the implementation.*
- d) *Disregarding others' suggestions or excluding them from discussions about problem-solving or modifications.*
- e) *They disregard the individual needs of individuals inside the company or team.*
- f) *They often make choices alone and without engaging other stakeholders.*
- g) *They exhibit an inflated feeling of self-importance and a misguided belief in their knowledge.*
- h) *They are too preoccupied with their self-image and anticipate others to reflect a certain persona.*
- i) *They anticipate becoming the epicenter of authority, accompanied by a perception of personal and professional supremacy.*
- j) *They esteem the company's senior leaders and endeavor to cultivate proximity to them.*

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- k) *They use punishment and manipulation by invoking emotions of guilt, fear, and humiliation to secure compliance and control.*
- l) *They have excessively competitive conduct.*
- m) *They seek methods to individualize the achievements of the team and its members.*

4. Conclusion

Manipulative conduct is intrinsically linked to narcissism. This may show as many demands for favors, courteous denigrations, actions that undermine your self-esteem, or similar behaviors. Maintain a firm grip on your ego boundaries, regardless of whether the individual is your supervisor. This is essential for declining a charming narcissist. A narcissist whom you do not see as exceptional will not concede defeat, yet will withdraw. For instance, a countdown timer may be used to provide equal speaking time to all participants in a meeting. Presenting a tangible fact in opposition to narcissistic manipulation is very successful, since it underscores their subjection to this reality.

You may compel an individual who makes a negative assertion, presuming your lack of comprehension, to articulate their meaning verbally by repeating their remark. When interacting with a narcissist who disregards or diminishes your presence, consider using textual communication techniques similar to those used when addressing your superiors. A high-functioning narcissist may be among the most effective workers in an organization provided they channel their energy into the appropriate department and job role. This circumstance may be transformed into an advantage by effective communication with them.

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Appendix-1 Scale Items

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Lütfen aşağıdaki ifadeleri okuduktan sonra kendinizi değerlendirip sizin için en uygun seçeneği işaretleyiniz.

	Tamamen Kabulmıyorum					Tamamen Kabuluyorum
	①	②	③	④	⑤	
1						① ② ③ ④ ⑤
2						① ② ③ ④ ⑤
3						① ② ③ ④ ⑤
4						① ② ③ ④ ⑤
5						① ② ③ ④ ⑤
6						① ② ③ ④ ⑤
7						① ② ③ ④ ⑤
8						① ② ③ ④ ⑤
9						① ② ③ ④ ⑤
10						① ② ③ ④ ⑤
11						① ② ③ ④ ⑤
12						① ② ③ ④ ⑤
13						① ② ③ ④ ⑤

ABOUT THE AUTHOR

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Ozgul COMEZ

Ozgul Comez; She is a master's student in Clinical Psychology at the St. Clements University. She completed her BA in Sociology at Anadolu University and in Psychology at University of Northwest. She is currently working as a Psychologist and Family Counselor at Armoni Psychology Academy. You can reach her at ozgulcomez@gmail.com.

Dr. Pamir DIRIL

Dr. Pamir Diril, He is a lecturer in the Turkish Department at St. Clements University. Pamir Diril graduated from the Department of Psychology. Pamir Diril completed his MA in the Department of Clinical Psychology with his thesis titled “Cognitive Behavioral Therapy for Cognitive Impairment in Schizophrenia” and his PhD in the Department of He completed his thesis titled “Psychological and sociological effects of domestic violence” at St. Clements University Department of Clinical Psychology. Dr. Pamir Diril has scientific articles in many

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international and national refereed journals. Dr. Diril is currently is an associate professor in the Department of Psychology at St. Clements University.